

PINK - Provision of Integrated Computational Approaches for Addressing New Markets Goals for the Introduction of Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design Chemicals and Materials

Safe-and-Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) advanced materials and chemicals (AdMas&Chems) are a central requirement for reaching the ambitious goal of making Europe the first digitally-enabled circular, climate-neutral and sustainable economy. Such new AdMas&Chems need to provide the high functionality required for their advanced applications, whilst simultaneously exhibiting improved safety and sustainability performances that take into account the complete value chain and life cycle, as outlined in the SSbD framework proposed by the EU Joint Research Centre and adopted in the Commission Recommendation of 8 Dec. 2022. To facilitate adoption by industry and, by doing so, foster the twin green and digital transition of Europe's economy, PINK's overarching aim is to produce innovative modelling software and integrated workflows for the development of AdMas&Chems, which are combined into an industry-ready open innovation platform, the PINK In Silico Hub (PINKISH).

PINK takes a holistic approach (see Figure 1) addressing the needs of industry by solving a multi-objective optimisation problem to improve and balance the four requirement categories functionality, cost-efficiency, safety and sustainability. All five steps of the SSbD Framework (hazard assessment, human health and safety aspects in the production and processing phase, human health and environmental aspects in the final application phase, environmental sustainability assessment, and socio-economic sustainability assessment) are integrated into selection considerations at each stage of the AdMas&Chems development, starting with a limited set of evaluation criteria and rough estimates (low-tier methods) and moving to higher-tier methods in later stages. In this way, confidence in the predictions is continuously improved over multiple design cycles by producing new knowledge on a constantly reduced set of better performing candidates.

PINK combines computational models and a decision support system (DSS) that exploit the combined power of first-principles simulation and pre-existing data, which - in itself - is further improved by advanced artificial intelligence (AI) technology. This requires the integration of tools from different and hitherto independently developed areas (e.g. materials modelling, (nano)safety, life cycle assessment). PINK provides this integration in the form of PINKISH based on an advanced semantic and technical Interoperability Framework, giving access to all information and knowledge, and executing SSbD workflows customisable to (a) the application area of the AdMas&Chems, (b) their safety and sustainability concerns of the existing materials, and (c) the status of the relevant development project (from early design ideas to registration and market entry). Industry readiness of the solution will be guaranteed by improving usability, practicability, user experience, and 'data provenance' documentation and security and by integrating these as important aspects into the development of new modelling software and decision support services. The sequence of implementation of the tools will be customised to real-life needs, to improve existing and new AdMas&Chems by industry partners in the PINK Developmental Case Studies and Industrial Demonstrators.

Accordingly, PINK's central objectives can be summaries as:

- develop a toolbox of data resources, models and workflows (PINK Services), benefitting from the interoperability and synergy of integrated approaches and provide them as openly accessible software tools and web services;
- build a framework and toolset for technical and semantic interoperability (Interoperability Framework and Infrastructure), based on high FAIRness (findable, accessible, interoperable and reusable) standards essential for information transfer within PINK and enabling re-use by other SSbD workflows or platforms;
- integrate all data and modelling services into the PINKISH platform to facilitate data visualisation, analysis, and the implementation of a comprehensive AI-enabled SSbD decision support workflow; and
- showcase how the computational and digital approaches can boost the innovative capacity of industry and especially SMEs in Developmental Case Studies and Industrial Demonstrators providing real-world stress testing of the provided solutions.

PINK has received funding from

the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. 101137809.

Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
Confederaziun svizra

Swiss Confederation

Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
Education and Research EAER
State Secretariat for Education,
Research and Innovation SERI

Innovate
UK

Specific activities will be:

- REFINE (WP1) and constantly reconfirm the industrial relevance and readiness of the PINK R&I Strategy based on the needs of all and especially industry stakeholders as well as lead harmonisation and engagement with different sustainability, industry, technology, and regulatory communities.
- INNOVATE (WP2) new computational approaches for AdMas&Chems development and for assessing their safety and sustainability performances by (a) integrating data and predictive models and (b) complement them with new AI techniques for data searches.
- INTEGRATE (WP3) these into a computational SSbD Framework by translating industrial requirements and new market demands into decision support as well as training and skill development needs.
- PROVIDE (WP4) an integrated platform, the PINKISH Platform, providing decision support based on advanced data visualisation and Generative AI technologies based on all generated data.
- FAIRIFY (WP5) the information exchange along the value-chain and life cycle of AdMas&Chems by developing an advanced Interoperability Framework, sharing the corresponding approaches and FAIR tools with the communities, and making data, models, workflows and software FAIR and whenever possible publicly available.
- VALIDATE (WP6) the newly developed PINK models and software as well as the PINKISH platform on two Developmental Case-Studies.
- BOOST (WP7) the innovation capacity of industry in general, and that of SMEs in particular, by making all PINK innovations accessible, promoting the cost-effective tools, further demonstrate these in at least three Industrial Demonstrators, and encouraging their sharing and use through dedicated training and skills development. This will be the starting point for implementing a business plan for commercialisation and long-term sustainability of the platform.

More information is available at <https://pink-project.eu> or by contacting thomas.exner@sevenpastnine.com.

Figure 1: Schematic presentation of the PINK R&I Approach of integrating the SSbD Framework into the development cycle of AdMas&Chems. This will be achieved by solving the multi-objective optimisation problem (middle part) to improve and balance the four requirement categories (i.e. functionality, cost-efficiency, safety and sustainability, lower part) at each stage of the development. Existing data will be integrated and data gaps be filled using innovative modelling and simulation approaches from the complete life cycle and value chain (upper part).

The PINK Consortium

Short Name - Organisation Name	Country
7P9-SI – Seven Past Nine d.o.o.	Slovenia
7P9-DE – Seven Past Nine GmbH	Germany
AIST – AcumenIST SPRL	Belgium
SINTEF – SINTEF AS	Norway
SO – SINTEF OCEAN AS	Norway
CNR – Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche	Italy
NTUA – Ethnicon Metsovion Polytechnion	Greece
NovaM – Novamechanics Limited	Cyprus
LIST – Luxembourg Institute of Science and Technology	Luxembourg
UH – Helsingin Yliopisto	Finland
KI – Karolinska Institutet	Sweden
PLUS – Paris-Lodron-Universität Salzburg	Austria
BASF – BASF SE	Germany
EMIRI – Energy Materials Industrial Research Initiative	Belgium
UoB – University of Birmingham	United Kingdom
EMPA – Eidgenössische Materialprüfungs- und Forschungsanstalt	Switzerland